

THE BEHAVIOUR OF BORON-ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES DURING AND AFTER IMPACT

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Two types of boron aluminium composites, having matrices of A4 and 2024-T4 alloy, have been tested in a circular bending machine which allows the maximum load each cycle to be maintained constant. The behaviour of the two types of material is different. The SN Curve for the B-2024-T4 specimen shows three regions, quasi static failure, progressive fibre failure and matrix cracking which does not produce fibre failure. The SN curve for the B-A4 is shown to be flat as the damaged zone is localised by longitudinal cracking of the matrix. Acoustic emission recording have been made in order to monitor the damage which occurs during the tests.

Introduction

Boron fibres have to a great extent been eclipsed by carbon fibres as the reinforcing agent for many composite applications but as a reinforcement, having exceptionally high specific properties, for metal matrix composites they remain largely unchallenged. Although an aluminium matrix is less fragile and so tougher than the commonly used organic matrix materials it has been known for some considerable time that one of the major problems for the use of all high performance composite materials in their fragility under impact (1). Due to their high intrinsic cost boron fibres are mainly attractive for applications for which their specific properties are a more important consideration than initial cost. This obviously means that the aerospace industry is a potential user of this material and for many of the applications in this domain the problem of impact and the possible fatigue failure of impacted parts is paramount.

It has been shown by a number of studies of various different types of composite materials that the damage produced by an impact depends on the properties of the fibre and not the matrix and that fibre damage was greatest with low fibre breaking strain (2,3). This damage however can be localised by the failure of the fibre matrix interface and this could occur in a fatigue situation.

Studies of the fatigue properties of B-Al in which specimens were tested in circular bonding, in which a constant moment is applied to the pivoted grips, have suggested that impact damaged specimens have better properties than undamaged specimens(4).

These studies leave however many questions still unanswered concerning the impact behaviour and the mechanisms involved in this type of damage of B-Al, particularly in loading situations similar to those likely to be encountered in reality. It is towards this end that this study has been directed and has involved an investigation of the controlling mechanics involved in the damage by impact of B-Al and the behaviour of the material in a fatigue situation.

Materials Tested

Two types of matrix material has been considered in this study, industrially pure aluminium (A4) and the aluminium 2024.T4 alloy. The boron fibres have been obtained from Composites Materials Corporation, U.S.A. and were of 100, 142 and 200 μ m diameter. The boron fibres have been filament wound on to a drum and glued together by a projection of polystyrene which permits a sheet of aligned fibres to be removed from the drum. Plates of B-Al were then made by sandwiching the fibres between sheets of the matrix material. This sandwich structure was the hot pressed under vacuum at temperatures and pressures which depended on the matrix material and which produced diffusion bonding. The polystyrene was removed during this process during a period of out-gassing. The volume fraction normally chosen to be 55% was controlled by the thickness of the sheets of matrix material and the gauge spacing of the fibres. Table 1 gives details of the elaboration conditions for the material used in this study as well as the dimensions of the flat rectangular specimens which were tested.

Table 1 - Details of fabrication

Componants		Arrangement		
Diameter of Boron fibres	Matrix	Pitch for fibres	Thickness of Al. sheets	Nos of fibre layers
142	A4	170	100	5
142	2024-T4	170	2 x 50	5

Elaboration			Dimensions		
Temperature °C	Duration mins	Pressure MPa	Thickness mm	Width mm	Length mm
540	60	35	1.06	18	60
485	60	45	1.06	18	60

Monotonic Loading

The full details of the monotonic tests covering a range of speeds from 2×10^{-3} mm/s to 4×10^3 mm/s, from slow penetration of either a 6 mm diameter steel ball or a steel bar of 5 mm diameter and length 12 mm to the impact of a projectile 10 mm wide and having a semi cylindrical leading edge of 5mm diameter, will be given elsewhere and only the results cited here (5). No speed effect was found in the range of speeds of impact used and it was considered that the situations considered were similar to a conventional micro hardness test. After yield the penetration was linearly related to the applied load. With the spherical indenter the circular deformation produced in the non-reinforced matrix material takes on an elliptical form because of the restraining influence of the fibres which were aligned parallel to the minor axis of the ellipsis, Figure 1. The ratio of the major axis (a) to the minor axis (b) for different composites with a loading of 100 kg is shown in Table 2. The reinforcement by the boron fibres means that a greater contact pressure is necessary to produce plastic déformation of the matrix as is shown in Figure 2.

Table 2 - Ratio of axes of the elliptical depression produced in the composites by a spherical indenter.

Ratio of axes	B(100)A4	B(142)A4	B(200)A4	B(142)2024-T4
$\frac{a}{b}$	1.58	1.38	1.24	1.12

Figure 1 - Elliptical imprint produced by spherical indenter due to restraining effect of the boron fibres.

Figure 2 - Microhardness as a function of pression for the non-reinforced and reinforced aluminium A4.

Figure 3 - Energy absorbed as a function of the penetrating load for the spherical indenter.

Figure 4 - Energy absorbed as a function of the penetrating load for the cylindrical indenter.

With the cylindrical indenter the loading occurred along a line or strip of material and in these experiments this was perpendicular to the fibre direction. The pressure needed to produce plastic deformation was increased compared to that necessary for a spherical indenter as the plastic deformation of the matrix was no longer possible. Table 3 gives the values obtained. The energy absorbed by the composite during the penetration tests are shown in Figures 3 and 4 as a function of the maximum loads for the two types of penetrators used.

Table 3 - Pressures to produce plastic flow with a cylindrical indenter.

	B(100)A ⁴	B(142)A ⁴	B(200)A ⁴	B(142) 2024-T4
\bar{P} MPa	860	840	680	2240

Fractographic and metallographic observations of the fibres broken under impact (Figure 5) show that failure occurred in the zone of contact. The fibres can be seen to have broken after crack initiation on the tensile side of the flexed fibre.

Figure 5 - Boron fibres broken directly under the point of impact.

Experimental Technique

The monotonic loading described above was conducted on an Instron tensile testing machine of 10 tonne capacity. In addition an instrumental impact machine has been constructed consisting of a steel projectile 10 mm wide and having a semicylindrical leading edge of 5 mm diameter. The loading involved during impact was measured by semiconductor strain gauges attached to the projectile 3 mm from the point of contact with the specimen which rested on a support of a moraging steel. The signal was stored on an oscilloscope having a memory facility.

A fatigue machine has been developed which cyclically tests rectangular specimens in circular bending and to a constant maximum load even though degradation may cause the compliance of the specimen to vary. The apparatus is shown schematically in Figure 6. The load on the specimen is transmitted by means of four chains which engage on the sprocket wheels fixed firmly to the grips of the machine which hold the specimen. Using the classical beam formula :

$$\frac{2\sigma}{B} = \frac{M}{I} \quad (1)$$

Where σ is the maximum tensile stress in the beam, B is the thickness, I the moment of inertia of the beam and M is the turning moment applied to the beam we can write for the elastic case considered :

$$\sigma = \frac{6M}{B^2W} = \frac{3dP}{B^2W} \quad (2)$$

Where P is the tension applied to the chains and d is the diameter of the sprocket.

The loading of the system takes place through a spring of high compliance by means of a rigid arm pivoted at the end not attached to the spring and which is either driven through an eccentric cam by an electric motor. The compliance (c) of the spring was 1.3 mm/kg and the compliance (c) of the system and specimen was typically 0.11 mm/kg.

As the deflection (D) of the machine was constant we can write

$$D = (c + c) F \quad (3)$$

if the compliance c changes by Δc because of damage to the specimen, we can write :

$$\frac{\Delta F}{F} = - \frac{\Delta c}{c + c} = \frac{-c}{c + c} \times \frac{\Delta c}{c} \quad (4)$$

Then the variation of load (ΔF) varies in the ratio of the variation of compliance :

$$\left| \frac{\Delta F}{F} \right| = \frac{c}{c} \left| \frac{\Delta c}{c} \right| \quad (5)$$

As the variation of compliance of the specimen is rarely more than 10% we can calculate the maximum variation of the load (F) applied using the values of compliances for the system which are given above :

$$\frac{\Delta F}{F} = \frac{0.11}{1.3} \times 0.1 \times 100 \approx 1\% \quad (6)$$

Figure 6 - Schematic view of the bending fatigue apparatus.

This type of circular bending fatigue machine maintain constant the maximum load applied to the specimen, even if its compliance changes to within 1%. The frequency of loading with this apparatus was 6 Hz.

In addition to the mechanical testing equipment a Dunegan-Endevco acoustic emission system was used to detect the mechanism which produced stress wave emission. In these tests a gain of 60 db or less has been used which allowed the detection of fibres breaks and important sudden fractures of the matrix. The A.E. transducer was either coupled directly to the specimen by silicone grease as in the case of the slow impact tests or to the pivoted grips in the fatigue experiments.

Other means of examination employed were optical and scanning electron microscopy and X-ray radiography.

Residual Properties and Fatigue Behaviour

It has been shown that in monotonic tensile tests centrally impacted specimens behave in a similar manner to that of centrally partially notched specimens (5). There was no detectable effect of stress concentration due to the notch nor the damaged zone and the strength of the composite was linearly related to the number of intact fibre layers.

For the circular bending fatigue tests both undamaged and impacted specimens have been used. Figures 7 and 8 show the SN curves obtained for undamaged specimens of each type of matrix. For the B-2024-T4 specimens three zones can be discerned.

i) a region of quasi static fracture at high loads and short lifetimes less than 10^4 cycles, during which the behaviour is controlled by the failure of the fibres,

ii) intermediate lifetimes during which stress concentrations in the matrix produce progressive fibre failures which can be detected by the acoustic emission technique,

iii) the emission recorded in the runout stage indicates that fibres are not being broken but that cracks, usually parallel to the fibres, are created and that rubbing of the fracture surfaces produce large bursts of acoustic activity.

The SN curve for the B-A4 specimens is much flatter and does not show these three zones described above. The lower yield point of the A4 matrix means that it is unable to transmit such high stress concentrations as is possible with the 2024-T4 and therefore progressive fibre failure does not occur.

Figures 9 and 10 show the SN curves for both types of impacted specimens with the curves of undamaged specimens shown as dotted lines. The stresses were calculated with respect to the reduced section. Both types of composite shows crack growth in the first few cycles during which the matrix bridge in the fibre damaged zone is fractured. During the course of cycling, cracking, both transverse and longitudinal to the fibre direction, has been observed.

For the B-2024-T4 transverse cracking including fibre failure occurred over a wide range of cycles and supports the possibility that stress concentrations induced by cracking of the matrix are sufficient to produce failure of the fibres although it has also been observed that work hardening of the matrix can be the cause of load transfer and failure of fibres neighbouring an initial fibre break without cracking of the matrix. It can also be seen from Figure 10 that the effect of the damage becomes of less importance at longer lifetimes as the curves for the damaged and undamaged specimens conver-

Figure 7 - SN Curve in circular bending of undamaged B-A4

Figure 8 - SN Curve in circular bending of undamaged B-2024-T4.

Figure 9 - SN Curve for impacted B-A4 together with the undamaged behaviour shown in Figure 7.

Figure 10 - SN Curve for impacted B-2024-T4 together with undamaged curve shown in Figure 8.

ge. This is due to the isolation of the damaged zone by longitudinal cracking parallel to the fibre direction. The curve for the damaged B-A⁴ specimens is flat indicating that the damaged zone is localised and the specimen behaves as though its cross sectional area had been reduced.

Conclusion

The behaviour of cyclically loaded specimen of A⁴ which had been impacted was that of specimen having a reduced cross section as the damage produced is quickly localised by longitudinal cracking parallel to the fibres. The behaviour of B-2024-T⁴ specimen is different and progressive fibre failure can occur during cycling which considerably reduces the strength of the material.

References

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